

THE COLORIMETRIC (*p*-DIMETHYLAMINOBENZALDEHYDE-SULPHURIC ACID) METHOD FOR DETERMINING SMALL QUANTITIES OF ATROPINE.

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A simple colorimetric method for the estimation of small quantities of atropine is recorded. Conditions for the optimum colour intensity have been obtained, and under the conditions laid down, the relationship between colour intensity and quantity of atropine is shown to be linear.

In the course of an investigation on the isolation and separation of the main constituents of *Datura* seeds, it became necessary to determine small quantities of atropine of the order of 0.1 to 0.5 mg. in small samples.

Existing methods, namely,

(i) Vitali's reaction ("L'Orosi," 1880; No. 8; *Arch. Phar.*, 1881, *iii*, 18, 307).

(ii) Physiological test.

(iii) Gold chloride test.

(iv) Eder's micro tests with bromine water and bromo-potassium bromide ("Micro-sublimation in vacuo" Zurich, 1912).

(v) Gulielmo's odour test. (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1863, 2, 404).

(vi) Gerrard's test. (*J. Pharm.*, 1884, 718).

being qualitative in nature, were valueless for quantitative assay.

Morin (*J. Pharm. chim.*, 1936, 128, 545) used Vitali's reaction (*loc. cit.*) for the determination of small amounts of atropine. For a quantity of 0.5 to 1.0 mg the colour is stated to be stable for 10 to 15 minutes and is intense violet. This method was found not sufficiently rapid for routine analysis.

Wasicky (*Z. anal. chem.*, 1915, 54, 393) noted the formation of a violet colour when atropine was warmed gently with *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde-sulphuric acid reagent. According to Wasicky this is as delicate as the physiological test. A preliminary investigation showed that this reaction offered considerable promise.

An exhaustive examination of the reaction showed that the time, temperature and the concentration of the reagents influenced the colour intensity.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Procedure.—Wasicky's reagent was used for the preliminary experiments. 1 ml. of a standard solution of atropine in 10% sulphuric acid (*w/v*) (1.0 mg. of atropine per ml.) was introduced into each of the four thin glass dishes, containing a drop of the reagent. The dishes were heated on a water-bath for 30 minutes. After making the coloured solutions up to 50 ml. in graduated flasks, the colours were matched against permanent glass standards in a Lovibond-Schofield tintometer. The results are as follows:

TABLE I.

1.0 Mg. in each dish using 10 cm. cell for a period of 30 min.

Flask No.	Tintometer reading.			Flask No.	Tintometer reading.		
	Red.	Blue.	Scale reading.		Red.	Blue.	Scale reading.
1	0.9	0.1	+0.06	3	1.0	0.1	+0.06
2	0.8	0.1	+0.05	4	0.9	0.1	+0.06

It was found that violet colour appeared after 10 minutes' heating. The readings were taken immediately after dilution, as the colour subsequently faded.

Next, the time of heating was varied. The dishes were heated for one hour on a water-bath, and the colours matched as before.

TABLE II.

1.0 Mg. in each dish using 10 cm. cell for a period of 60 min.

Flask No.	Tintometer reading.			Flask No.	Tintometer reading.		
	Red.	Yellow.	Scale reading.		Red.	Yellow.	Scale reading.
1	4.1	0.8	+0.30	3	3.9	0.8	+0.24
2	4.0	0.9	+0.25	4	4.2	0.7	+0.31

The results indicate that the colour produced is not violet but orange, and in every case the tintometer reading (red) is higher than 30 minutes' heating experiments (Table I).

Effect of the Concentration of the Reagent.—A series of determinations were made using 0.1 ml. of the reagent. In previous experiments only one drop of the reagent was used.

The results in Table III indicate that the quantity of the reagent added also influences the colour intensity. Once again maximum red is obtained but the colour is orange. This colour is rather difficult to match, and is stable for ten minutes.

It was found that in order to obtain optimum violet colour, heating for 30 minutes was sufficient, and that the yellow colour was due to the strong reagent. The reagent was diluted 1:1 with water and 0.1 ml. of the dilute reagent was used in the following experiments.

The standard solution of atropine was introduced into each of the four dishes, and heated with 0.1 ml. of the dilute reagent for 30 minutes on a water-bath. The colours were matched as before after making up to 25 ml. in graduated flasks.

TABLE III.

1.0 Mg. in each dish using 10 cm. cell and 0.1 ml. of the reagent. Heating time = 60 min.

Time after dilution.	Tintometer reading.			Time after dilution.	Tintometer reading.		
	Red.	Yellow.	Scale reading.		Red.	Yellow.	Scale reading.
	Flask No. 1				Flask No. 2		
0 min.	7.1	3.2	+0.36	5 min.	7.2	3.1	+0.35
5	7.1	3.2	+0.36	25	6.4	3.0	+0.35
10	7.0	3.0	+0.35	30	6.2	2.9	+0.34
15	6.8	2.9	+0.34	40	6.1	2.8	+0.35
	Flask No. 3				Flask No. 4		
5 min.	7.1	3.0	+0.35	5 min.	7.1	3.1	+0.35
15	6.7	2.9	+0.34	30	6.1	2.8	+0.34
30	6.1	2.8	+0.35	45	5.9	2.7	+0.33
40	6.0	2.9	+0.34	50	5.6	2.6	+0.33

TABLE IV.

Using 2 cm. cell and 0.1 ml. of the dilute reagent. Heating time = 30 min. The colour when undiluted is stable, but slowly fades when diluted with water.

Atropine.	Tintometer reading.			Atropine.	Tintometer reading.		
	Red.	Blue.	Scale reading.		Red.	Blue.	Scale reading.
0.55 mg.	3.3	0.2	+0.10	1.40	8.3	0.5	+0.35
0.65	3.9	0.2	+0.15	1.45	8.7	0.5	+0.40
0.95	5.7	0.3	+0.23	1.65	9.9	0.6	+0.45
1.35	8.1	0.5	+0.34				

The results (Table IV) obtained with this dilute reagent are of importance as the colour produced is violet and is suitable for colorimetric work.

The method as finally adopted.—The reagents used were :

(i) *p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde-sulphuric acid.—2.0 G. of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, dissolved in 10 ml. of concentrated sulphuric acid. This yellowish brown solution keeps for about four weeks if stored in dark.

(ii) *Dilute reagent.*—The reagent (i) is diluted 1:1 with water before use. This reagent should be prepared fresh every day.

(iii) Standard solution of atropine in sulphuric acid.

0.1 Ml. of the reagent was added to the glass dish (10 ml. capacity) containing atropine. The glass dish was heated for 30 to 40 minutes on a water-bath. The solution was poured into a 25 ml. graduated flask, and diluted to the mark with water. The colour was immediately matched against permanent glass standards in the tintometer.

In general, colours of low intensity (0.1 to 1.0 mg. of atropine) were fully developed in 30 minutes whilst deeper colours (more than 1 mg. of atropine) required 40 minutes.

A number of determinations (Table V) was made, using the above method and the standard solution of atropine.

TABLE V.

Using the Lovibond-Schofield tintometer, cell = (2.0 cm.)

Atropine.	Red.	Blue	Scale reading. (+)	Total visual density.	Brightness.	Dominant hue-wave-length mg. (Centre B).	Saturation L P. D. (Centre B).
0.1 mg.	0.7	—	0.05	0.075	84.14%	509.0 mg.	3.5
0.2	1.2	0.1	0.06	0.13	74.13	508.5	7.0
0.3	1.8	0.1	0.07	0.17	67.61	505.0	10.0
0.4	2.5	0.2	0.10	0.215	60.95	504.0	14.0
0.5	3.1	0.2	0.10	0.26	54.95	503.0	17.5
0.6	3.6	0.2	0.15	0.32	47.86	503.0	21.0
0.7	4.2	0.3	0.20	0.385	42.17	502.5	25.0
0.8	4.9	0.3	0.20	0.425	37.58	502.5	28.0
0.9	5.5	0.3	0.23	0.50	31.62	502.2	31.5
1.0	6.0	0.3	0.24	0.54	28.84	502.0	35.0
1.1	6.7	0.4	0.25	0.60	25.12	502.0	38.0
1.2	7.2	0.4	0.30	0.65	22.39	501.5	41.5
1.3	7.8	0.5	0.34	0.72	19.05	501.4	45.0
1.4	8.4	0.5	0.35	0.76	17.38	501.0	49.0
1.5	9.0	0.5	0.40	0.82	15.14	501.0	52.0
1.6	9.7	0.5	0.40	0.85	14.13	500.2	55.1
1.7	10.3	0.6	0.45	0.91	12.3	500.0	59.0

The standard working curve for the determination of atropine illustrates the linear relation between colour intensity and concentration of atropine.

Analyses of the colour saturation and of the brightness were also made. There is a regular rate of increase of the colour saturation with the quantity of atropine. The transmission of light decreases fairly regularly as the quantity of atropine increases to 1.5 mg., and then becomes fairly constant.

In order to eliminate any possibility of error from the reagents, a second quantity was prepared, and a series of determinations made with atropine as before. The results (Table VI) agreed with those obtained with the first quantity of reagent.

TABLE VI.

Using the second stock of reagents; cell = 2 cm.

Atropine.	Tintometer reading.			Atropine.	Tintometer reading.		
	Red	Blue	Scale reading.		Red	Blue	Scale reading.
0.50 mg.	3.1	0.2	+0.10	1.00	6.1	0.3	+0.24
0.65	3.8	0.2	0.15	1.35	8.1	0.5	0.34
0.70	4.1	0.3	0.20	1.45	8.7	0.5	0.40
0.95	5.6	0.3	0.23				

Evaporation of Atropine in Sulphuric Acid Solution.

A solution of atropine in an excess of dilute sulphuric acid can be evaporated down to 0.5-1.0 ml. approximately without loss. This was tested by introducing equal quantities of atropine into separate dishes containing 1 ml. of 10% sulphuric acid; then 10 ml. of water were added and the solution was evaporated down to 1 ml. by heating on a water-bath. The atropine in each dish was then determined, and the differences were within the experimental error.

Analytical Data.—The results obtained on known concentration of atropine, ranging between 0.1 mg. to 1.0 mg., using the above mentioned method are given in Table VII.

TABLE VII.

Recovery of known amounts of atropine.

Atropine in solution.	Atropine found from the standard curve	Recovery.	Difference
0.100	0.095	95.0	- 5.0
0.100	0.090	90.0	- 10.0
0.500	0.475	95.0	- 5.0
0.500	0.500	100.0	0
1.00	1.00	100.0	0
1.00	0.975	97.5	- 2.5

They show good recovery of amounts of atropine ranging between 1.0 to 0.1 mg. With smaller amounts, viz. 0.1 mg., the recovery was about 10% lower than the theoretical yield.

The above method has been employed most advantageously for making numerous routine estimations of atropine. The method is being extended to determine small quantities of scopolamine and hyoscyamine.

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